

BETANIN- PROPERTIES & THERAPEUTIC BENEFITS**¹*Ruby Santra and ²Dr. Kamalakanta Ray**^{1,2}JIS University, Department of Pharmaceutical Technology, Kolkata-81, West Bengal-700109.Article Received on
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of Pharmaceutical
Technology, Kolkata-81,
West Bengal- 700109.**1. ABSTRACT**

With the enhanced researches and studies upon phytochemicals, it is being found that phytomedicines can prove to be safer and equivalently active as synthetic medicines. And since, there are numerous such phytochemicals been found and still are being researched which are having various vital therapeutic activities, whether it is antiviral or anticancer, phytochemicals can treat such disease conditions with equivalent effect along with minimal side effects. Thus, demand and researches upon phytomedicines are increasing day by day. One of such vital phytochemical is Betanin, found mostly in beetroot, which has found to have many additive action such as colourant, pH indicator

as well as therapeutical activity such as anticancer, antidiabetic, antimicrobial activities. In this article, a detailed review upon various therapeutical activities along with its mechanism and benefit in comparison to synthetic drug for such disease conditions have been discussed.

2. KEYWORDS: Betanin; Oxidative stress; Free radical scavenger; Cancer cell suppressor; Serum insulin elevator; ROS; RNS.

3. INTRODUCTION

Phytochemicals are well known to have significant decreasing impact against the risk of various fatal degenerative and chronic diseases. Thus, in the present era the use of natural medicines have enhanced mainly due to their low toxicity, eco-friendliness and good efficiency. Betanin (betanidin 5-β-D-glucoside), an water soluble natural pigment obtained from beets, *Beta vulgaris* L. and its aglycone form known as betanidin derived by removing the glucose molecule from betanin by hydrolysis, used mostly in food industry is found having good antioxidant properties, thus indicates to yield anti-inflammatory effect, hepatoprotective effect, anticarcinogenic effects.

Fig. 1: Structure of Betanin.

Chemically, betanin consist of aglycone betanidin in its structure i.e. β -glycoside linked with a glucose unit at carbon-5 position. Its molar mass is 550.47 gm/mol with chemical formula $C_{24}H_{26}N_2O_{13}$. Betanin along with isobetanin, probetanin & neobetanin belongs to betalain, a water soluble heterocyclic pigment contents of beetroot. Beetroot contains a group of both yellow and red pigments which is known as betalain of which the yellow pigments are known as betaxanthins of wavelength around 480 nm while red-violet pigments are known as betacyanins having wavelength around 540 nm. And betanin belongs to these red betacyanin pigments which is the crucial constituent in beetroots i.e. 75-95%. The colour of betanin changes from bluish-red to bluish-violet between pH 4.0-5.0 based on increase in pH, and thus is a pH sensitive dye. It remains stable between this pH range. Once the pH reaches 6 or above, it starts degrading by hydrolysis and appears as yellow-brown colour. It can also degrade at high temperature, light and also in presence of metals such as iron, copper. As a food additive, it has been approved by Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and European Union as a dye at quantum satis and coded as E162 (EFSA 2015; FDA, 2009). Approx 50% of orally administered betanin has the ability to resist stomach gastric acid and remains stable after intestinal digestion, at 37°C in GIT.(Tesorriere et al. 2008; Silva, Bai~ao, et al. 2019).

Fig. 2: Betanin decomposition by heating and hydrolysis.

SOURCES

Betanin is obtained commonly naturally from beet root (*Beta vulgaris L.*) which in English it's known as Beet root, Garden root or Table root, in Bengali it's Bitpalang, in Hindi it's Chukander, in Sanskrit it's called Palanki while in Tamil it's called Beet kilangu. Beet root is cultivated throughout India as vegetable. An optimum temperature of 16° C and sunshine weather is best for its growth (Har Bhajan Singh, Kumar Avinash Bharati, 2014).

Various other minor sources includes *Opuntia cactus*, *Swiss chard* and leaves of some species of *Amaranth*. According to various experiments, the contents of beetroot are water (87.1%), carbohydrate (7.6%), protein (1.7%), fat (0.1%), and betanin (0.03–0.06%).

Extraction

The root extracts contain betanin in a concentration of 300-600 mg/kg while other parts such as the peel, crown or flesh contains lesser amount as beet juice concentrate, dehydrated beet root or spray dried extract of which betanin is extracted by various chromatographic methods. The fermented extracted juice by *Torulopsis utilis* contains 5-7 times more concentration as fermentation reduces the total solids contents in the juice without altering the pigments (Har Bhajan Singh, Kumar Avinash Bharati, 2014).

Fig. 3: Separation of Betanin by HPLC-DAD monitored at 536 nm. (A) Chromatography of betanin standard in the analytical HPLC column, (B) Chromatography of fresh beetroot juice sample in semi-preparative HPLC, (C) Purification and separation of betanin by semi-preparative HPLC and an analytical HPLC column and (D) Evaluation of betanin after 275 days of freezing and chromatography of betanin using an analytical HPLC column. Betanin (peak 1) and isobetanin (peak 1').

VARIOUS USES AND ACTIVITIES

Betanin is used for various chemical synthesis process; as a natural food, cosmetic and pharmaceutical colorant; in various analytical studies. In food industries, betanin is useful as colorant for ice creams, soft drink beverages, sugar fondants, sugar coatings, sugar candies or cream fillings. It is also used for colouring meats and sausages. Betanin also has a good antioxidant, antiviral as well as antimicrobial properties. Hence, can also be used as natural preservatives.

Betanin is a free oxidative radicals scavenger. Its antioxidant power is due to the presence of hydroxyl group in the phenol part and the cyclic amine group, which makes it a good hydrogen donor and confer reducing properties (Kanner, Harel, and Granit, 2001;

Gliszczynska-Swigło, Szymusiak and Malinowska, 2006). And due to this antioxidant activity it provides numerous health benefits such as hepatoprotective activity, cardioprotective activity, anticarcinogenic activity and much more, and so it has become a significant vegetable extract of scientific interest.

Fig. 4: Betain extraction and activities.

Betain for anticancer activity

Cancer is one of the most lethal disease which is considered to be the second most common reason for death with millions of cases every year worldwide. And chemotherapy, which is one of the common treatment method of cancer is usually found to have low cellular uptake in the cancer cells with some disagreeable side effects that can further cause nephrotoxicity, hepatotoxicity, cardiotoxicity and other toxicities. Thus, approaches to alternatives are made to reduce side effects. Of which, using bioactive compounds alone or in combination with chemotherapy can help in lowering the side effects with a safe and effective alternative. In recent studies, beetroot have been found to exert cytotoxic effect on cancerous cell, thus preventing against cancer. Betain or its stereoisomer isobetain acts on cancerous cells by death signaling pathways and lowers cancer cell proliferation and viability without effecting normal cells. In MCF-7-treated cells, the expressions of apoptosis-related proteins (Bad, TRAILR4, FAS, p53) are strongly increased by betain and isobetain with autophasic cell death (Laëtitia Nowacki, Pascale Vigneron, Laura Rotellini, 2015).

Betanin if co-administered with other potent anticancer agents, such as doxorubicin, can lower the side effect of the drug on normal tissues due to its synergistic effect against cancerous cells and so, reduces the amount of anticancer drug required. Yet it has limitations such as incomplete oral absorption as well as poor stability. But it can be overcome to some extent by developing pH-responsive nanocarrier by using gelatin nanoparticles with (methoxy poly ethylene glycol)-poly (2-dimethylamino) ethyl methacrylate-co-itaconic acid) (PGNPs) which gives better drug release pattern and controlled release based on pH of the environment, also the synergistic effect of doxorubicin with betanin loaded PGNPs can lessen the cell viability amount, enhance cell uptake and induce apoptosis of breast cancer cells (MCF-7) more effectively than the free form of drugs (Sajed Amjadi, Hamed Hamishehkar, Marjan Ghorbani, 2018).

Betanin has also been found to induce apoptosis and produce significant cytotoxic effect on cancerous U87MG human glioma cells which is categorized as glioblastoma, ependymoma, astrocytoma, oligodendroglioma, and mixed glioma and the mode of action is induction of cellular apoptosis via mitochondrial pathway by activation of caspase-3 along with modulation of apoptosis-related mitochondria, along with increase in ROS formation, mitochondria swelling, MMP decrease as well as cytochrome C release in cancerous mitochondria. Glioblastoma, which is the most lethal form of brain cancer is generally treated with surgical incision along with daily radiation and oral chemotherapy with temozolamide. But yet, its fatal with poor recovery rate. Since, glioblastoma cells are usually characterized by dearranged, decoupled mitochondria and due to multidrug resistance as well as severe side effects of radiochemotherapy making the approach ineffective, natural biochemicals have proved to be a better alternative in malignant glioma cells and its mitochondria. Recent investigations have shown protective carcinogenesis role of beetroot extracts, especially betanin with cytotoxic effect on tumor cells by specifically targeting mitochondrial dysfunction. Thus, betanin with temozolamine proves to induce synergistic effect and thus can be a better alternative against p53 mutant and temozolamide-resistant glioma cell lines without affecting normal cell mitochondria (Ahmad Salimi, Tannaz Bahiraei, Sana Ahdeno, 2020).

Betanin for antidiabetic activity

Diabetes mellitus, which is one of the largest globally increasing non-communicable disease after cancer and cardiovascular disease, has a serious threat to public health. According to

WHO, number of diabetes cases between 2000-2016 lead to 5% premature death while in 2019, there were 1.5 million deaths due to diabetes. There are various types of medicines available to control blood glucose level, of which insulin is used to treat type-1 diabetes mellitus while various oral hypoglycemics are used to treat type-2 diabetes mellitus but to get proper treatment without any adverse effect is the biggest question of interest regarding diabetes, since these have high chances of secondary failure as well as side effects such as toxicity, discomfort, flatulence and diarrhoea. So, phytochemicals with potent antidiabetic action is the better alternative as they have low side effects with comparatively low cost of treatment. There are around 450 medicinal plants being clinically proved to have anti-diabetic activity of which 109 plants can provide complete cure against diabetes (Sonia Verma, Madhu Gupta, Harvinder Popli, 2018). One of the potent antidiabetic phytochemical found in beet root juice is betalain, of which 75-95% is betanin which are commonly used as food colorants, also consist of high free radical scavenging activity due its high proportion of phenolic and cyclic amine groups that make them good electron donors. But the problem related to just 1% bioavailability, high susceptibility to degradation under different conditions such as temperature, pH, oxygen and light reduces its effectiveness for which nanocarriers can be a better form to increase its stability. Fabrication of betanin into nanoliposome carrier can provide slow release pattern with good stability and antioxidant activity and can help to reduce body weight loss and blood glucose level as well as elevation of serum insulin level. It also helps to reduce tissue damage in kidney, liver and pancreas caused by hyperglycemia and oxidant stress, hence help to improve the quality of life of diabetic patients. Thus, betanin in nanoliposomal form with improved stability as well as bioavailability can be a better alternative treatment against diabetes (Sajed Amjadi, Mehran Mesgari Abbasi, Behrooz Shokouhi, 2019).

Betanin, the chromoalkaloids of beetroot can also provide protective action against hyperglycemia in streptozotocin (STZ) – nicotinamide (NA) induced diabetes type-2. Diabetes mellitus, which is characterized by hyperglycemic condition due to consequence of defective insulin secretion along with defect in carbohydrate metabolism, also indirectly affects the endocrine system. In type-1 diabetes, where the body is not able to produce enough insulin, increases glucose level while in type-2 diabetes, where body is unable to respond to insulin leads to increase in glucose level. Liver which is an insulin-sensitive organ plays a vital role in regulating glucose homeostasis by controlling glucose utilization i.e. glycolysis, glycogenesis and gluconeogenesis. The net amount of blood glucose level

depends upon the glucokinase and glucose-6-phosphatase activity. In diabetes, activity of hepatic glucokinase is decreased while activity of glucose-6-phosphatase is increased to about double times. The activity of these enzymes are controlled by insulin. And since the available oral hypoglycaemic drugs are costlier with adverse effects such as hypoglycemia, hepatotoxicity, dyslipidemia and attenuation of response after protracted use, various phytomedicines such as betalains have been proved to possess antidiabetic activity. Betanin, which constitute 75-95% of total betalain is found to significantly reduce postprandial glycemia by stimulation of insulin. Co-administration of betanin with glibenclamide significantly reduce the plasma glucose level and raise the insulin levels, also improves the enzymes activities of hepatic glucokinase, pyruvate kinase and glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase and decreases the glucose-6-phosphatase and fructose-1,6-bisphosphatase activity with decrease in glycogen level thereby maintaining the blood glucose homeostasis. Co-administration of betanin as well as glibenclamide also increases the total Hb levels due to improved blood glucose control. Thus betanin proves to enhance the glucose consumptions by declining the production of glucose in liver through insulin release and thus indicate its positive impact in the treatment of diabetes mellitus (Dhananjayan Indumathi, Kathioli Sujithra, Subramani Srinivasan, Veerasamy Vinothkumar, 2017).

While talking about various perspectives to overcome diabetes, diet routine and lifestyle is one of the crucial factors that has involvement in maintenance of blood sugar level, also involves in the hyperglycosylation of biomolecules as well as in the prevention of pathologies associated with that. In this concern, various biochemical constituents present in various natural sources like fruits, vegetables, dietary constituents etc. are being researched upon to find out their role in prevention and management of diabetes of which one of the natural diet source is beet. Beet contains numerous bioactive constituents such as polyphenols, flavonoids, ascorbic acid, betalains, therapeutic enzymes, and dehydroascorbic acid of which the antidiabetic constituent is betalain, flavonoids, pectin, and fibers. Approximately 2 g/kg extract of red beet for 28 days can increase the number of beta-cells and secretory granules in islet of Langerhans in STZ-induced diabetes while daily consumption of 100–200 gm of red beet along with horseradish can significantly reduce plasma sugar level in diabetic people (Josef et al, 1973). Betalain present in cactus pear, an important pigment of red beet is generally used by Mexicans and Italians to treat diabetes and are found to provide a better treatment in comparison to insulin treatment. Detroit red, a red beet cultivator has proved that feeding with 2 g/kg of beet powder for 10 days can reduce fatty liver symptoms, serum

cholesterol levels and changes alkaline phosphatase and alanine-aminotransferase activities in chemically induced diabetic animal model. And this function of red beet was found to be mainly due to betanin and polyphenol contents of the beet (Sardi et al. 2009). Thus from many such in vitro, pre-clinical and clinical investigations it can be said that various bioactive molecules and chemical constituents of red beet vegetables such as fiber, flavonoids, betacyanin, betaxanthin, pectin have the potentiality to reduce diabetes and related complications where the mode of action is mostly the antioxidant activity of bioactive molecules in red beet. Also, daily consumption of red beet and its juice have its impact in reduction of blood pressure by NO formation as well as mood elevation by its DOPA and NO actions that supports an overall health improvement status (Kotamballi N. Chidambara Murthy and Shivapriya Manchali, 2013).

Due to impaired metabolism in diabetes mellitus, also leads to oxidative stress by various mechanisms such as glucose autoxidation, protein glycation and AGEs formation that further leads to the development of secondary diabetic complications such as nephropathy, retinopathy, neuropathy, macro and microvascular damages. Diabetic nephropathy is the one significant cause of end stage renal disease (ESRD) in which oxidative stress is the root cause of kidney impairments such as acute and chronic renal failure, glomerular injury and obstructive nephropathy (Baliga et al., 1999, Fiorillo et al., 1998). Various studies have proved that the antioxidants have ability to attenuate free radical mediated diabetic nephropathy (Hahn et al., 1999, Melhem et al., 2001, Anjaneyulu et al., 2004). Betanin contains a phenolic and cyclic amine groups, which makes it good donor of electron, due to which it has exceptionally high free-radical scavenging ability, and betanin can distribute inside of cells. Betanin is also found to exhibit additional pharmacological effects on lipid byproducts and kidney biomarkers enzymes in both normal and STZ-NA induced diabetes. Hyperglycemia is found to significantly elevate the levels of some the vital biomarkers of renal dysfunction such as uric acid, urea and creatinine. The co-administration of betanin is found to have ability to decrease the levels of these biomarkers i.e. uric acid, urea and creatinine in STZ-NA induced diabetes, thus can recover renal function due to improved glycemic control. Thus betanin, a natural betacyanin pigment from the red beetroot can significantly decrease the peripheral glucose and improve the insulin secretion as well as alters the levels of lipid byproducts and renal biomarkers through its insulinotropic effect in STZ-NA induced type 2 diabetes, hence has renoprotective activity (Dhananjayan Indumathi, Kathioli Sujithra, 2017).

Betanin for hepatoprotective activity

Acute liver failure, also known as fulminant hepatic failure that causes serious complications such as excessive bleeding or increased pressure in brain, jaundice, abdominal swelling, nausea, vomiting and soon is generally caused by various over-the-counter pain medicines misuse or overdose through induction of oxidative stress with electrophilic metabolite N-acetyl-p-benzoquinone imine (NAPQI) of which the most common OTC medicine is acetoaminophen. At therapeutic dose, acetoaminophen gets metabolized by glucuronic acid or sulphate in the liver. Upto 90% of the drug undergoes excretion through urine and small amount is excreted unchanged while around 10% is metabolised by cytochrome P450 enzymes into a highly reactive intermediate N-acetyl-p-benzoquinone-imine (NAPQI), which is generally detoxified by conjugation with glutathione. But at high doses, the glucuronidation capacity gets saturated and glutathione is depleted. Thus, more of the NAPQI is formed which binds with proteins of liver cells causing hepatic cell necrosis. Till date, the only approved medicine for acetoaminophen overdose treatment is N-acetylcysteine (NAC), a precursor of glutathione. But in many cases NAC has been seem to be ineffective in treating liver necrosis, and then liver transplantation becomes the only way of treatment. Since plants contain various bioactive chemical compounds that have been a part of traditional medicine for a long time and they are found to be quite effective in the therapy and hindrance of various diseases (González-Ponce, Rincón-Sánchez, Jaramillo-Juárez, & Moshage, 2018), thus in Mexico, cactus species (*Opuntia* spp.) are used as a dietary component (Saenz, 2000) for their beneficial effects (Santos Díaz, Barba de la Rosa, Héliés-Toussaint, Guéraud, & Négre-Salvayre, 2017) like antioxidative effect (Coria Cayupán, Ochoa, & Nazareno, 2011), anti-inflammatory effect (Antunes-Ricardo, Gutiérrez-Urbe, López-Pacheco, Alvarez, & Serna-Saldívar, 2015), hepatoprotective action (González-Ponce et al., 2016), hypoglycemic effect (Leem, Kim, Hahm, & Kim, 2016), neuroprotective action (Dok-Go et al., 2003), anti-carcinogenic effect (Sreekanth et al., 2007), anti-atherogenic effect (Keller et al., 2015), and antigenotoxic effect (Brahmi et al., 2011). These effects are seemed because to the presence of certain bioactive molecules such as betalains, carotenoids and flavonoids and phenolic compounds. Of these bioactive components, betanin and isobetainin which is type of betalains are found to increase the antioxidant capacity rather than any other constituents of *Opuntia* cactus. The hepatoprotective effect in liver damage induced by the reactive free radical NAPQI is mainly produced by reduction of oxidative stress. In-vivo, *Opuntia* extracts are found to reduce the biochemicals that put their impact in liver damage; such as reduction of malondialdehyde and help to restore the levels of glutathione to reduce oxidative stress.

Specially the effect can be seen at centrilobular region i.e. zone III of acinus at liver where the expression of the cytochrome P450 2E1 is found to be strong; where APAP gets metabolized into the reactive metabolite NAPQI, hence betanin or isobetainin of *Opuntia cactus* improves the hepatic condition of that region (Abdelmegeed, Moon, Chen, Gonzalez, & Song, 2010). In-vitro, *Opuntia* extracts are found to reduce lactate dehydrogenase efflux into the medium and Sytox green nuclear staining, hence can reduce hepatic necrosis. Hence, *Opuntia robusta* and *Opuntia streptacantha* is found to have hepatoprotective action against APAP-induced hepatotoxicity of which *Opuntia robusta* comparatively appears to be slightly more protective in compare to the other one as the content of betacyanin is more in the former species rather than the later one (Herson Antonio González-Ponce, Ma. Consolación Martínez-Saldaña, Pieter G. Tepper, 2020).

Paracetamol and diclofenac, which are the most commonly used analgesic and anti-inflammatory drugs are mostly found to induce hepatic as well as renal damage. Administration of Paracetamol or Diclofenac in high dose and for long-time duration can induce liver and kidney injury along with disruption of serum lipid profile, increase in serum inflammatory and oxidative stress markers, increase in DNA fragmentation and causes drastic changes in the histopathological characteristics of both the organs. Analgesics and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are the most commonly used classes of medicines over the world (Nkoom et al., 2019). These are mostly non-prescription drugs used in treatment of mild-to-moderate pain and fever (Nasir, 2018). But the metabolic byproducts of these molecules such as Paracetamol, are generally reactive metabolites that has the ability to damage the cells (Abdeen et al., 2019). Although the effect of paracetamol overdose in hepatotoxicity is more common but along that, it also causes nephrotoxicity and acute renal failure. Similarly Diclofenac, an another commonly used NSAID for management of pain and inflammations such as rheumatoid arthritis (Ledakowicz et al., 2019) can also cause renal & hepatic failure. Diclofenac after metabolic activation gets converted into various hydroxylated metabolites such as 4-hydroxydiclofenac (4-OH-DF) and 5-hydroxydiclofenac (5-OH-DF). These metabolites further enzymatically or non-enzymatically gets oxidized into their corresponding p-benzoquinoneimines (Boerma et al., 2014). These reactive electrophilic benzoquinoneimine species may undergo covalent binding with non-proteinous or proteinous sulfhydryl groups to produce oxidative stress that is responsible for hepatic or renal damage (Peter and Prince, 2018). Studies for protective effect has shown that betanin, which is one of the 10 most potential water soluble nitrogen

containing antioxidant biomolecules found in red beet root (*Beta vulgaris*) and cactus pear fruit (*Opuntia ficus-indica*) (Han et al. 2015; Al-aboud, 2018).

Since plant extracts have proved to be beneficial in many health conditions and due to the side effects and expenses of modern medicines to manage hepatic diseases; beetroot juice extracts having potential hepatoprotective effect have widely gained interest recently for management of liver disease conditions. *Beta vulgaris* are mostly grown throughout Europe and North America and in some part of West Africa as beetroots grow well in cool conditions (Mitchell SC, 2001). Beetroot is a rich source of phytochemicals such as ascorbic acid, phenols, alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, saponins, phytosterols and glycosides and is also one of the few vegetables containing the bioactive pigment, betalains. And as betalains are found to have anti-inflammatory along with antioxidant activity both in-vitro and in-vivo animal models, so have possibilities in successful management of pathological conditions characterized by oxidative stress and chronic inflammation such as liver disease, arthritis and cancer. Liver as one of the vital organ in the body that is primarily responsible for the metabolism of endogenous and exogenous agents and in drug elimination and detoxification. Liver damage is mainly caused by xenobiotics, high alcohol consumption, malnutrition, infection, anaemia, and various medications. Various hepatotoxic agents react with the primary cellular components and thus induce almost all types of liver infections. Chemical hepatotoxic agents (such as acetaminophen, carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄), galactosamine, and thioacetamide) are commonly used as the model substances for inducing experimental hepatocyte injury in both in vivo and in vitro conditions. Among various, hepatotoxic agents, CCl₄ consumption has been found to cause centrilobular steatosis, inflammation, apoptosis, and necrosis by the action of cytochrome P-450 dependent reductive dehalogenation which gives a highly reactive bioactive trichloromethyl free radical CCl₃. The reactive free radicals of CCl₄ is responsible for increased lipid peroxidation which in turn is responsible for production of malondialdehyde, a cytotoxic byproduct of lipid peroxidation which finally leads to cell apoptosis and necrosis. If the damage is more than the repairing ability of the liver, it will lead to liver fibrosis and cirrhosis. Various plant extracts having antioxidant activity are found to provide protection against CCl₄ hepatotoxicity mostly by inhibition of lipid peroxidation and enhancement of antioxidant enzyme activity. A single dose of CCl₄ causes centrilobular necrosis and steatosis, while prolonged administration causes liver failure, cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma due to overproduction of CCl₃. The free radicals oxidatively damage mitochondria and regulate gene expression that contributes in

development of fibrosis and leads to chronic inflammatory processes. In chronic hepatocyte cirrhosis, ALT serum level increases more than AST, but as fibrosis progresses, periodically ALT level starts declining and the serum level of AST gradually increases, such that by the time cirrhosis is developed, AST is higher than ALT. Elevation of serum AST, ALT, and ALP levels by CCl₄ have attribution in hepatocytic lesion as these enzymes are generally present in the cytoplasm which gets released into the circulation after cellular damage occurs. Also weak cellular membranes are found to cause sufficient leakage of calcium into the cytosol and high calcium levels in the cytosol activate calcium-dependent proteases and phospholipases that can further elevate the breakdown of cell membranes (Manibusan MK, Odin M, Eastmond DA, 2007). Also the increase in MDA level when treated with CCl₄ leads to enhanced lipid peroxidation, causing tissue damage as well as failure of antioxidant defense mechanisms that prevent formation of excessive free radicals (Shenoy KA, Somayaji SN, Bairy KL, 2001). But through various research studies, it has been enlighten that some bioactive phytochemicals such as silymarin or beet root extracts like betalains have proved to upregulate the enzyme activities of ALT OR AST, reduce MDA levels, thus providing hepatoprotective action. At 500 mg of beet root extract and 100 mg/kg body weight of silymarin, the upregulation of ALT concentration can be observed which may be the influence of beetroot extracts that have the ability to regenerate liver tissue by retardation of cell necrosis or fibrosis processes, hence initiating the production of new cells. At around 500mg, the extract has the ability to prevent lipid peroxidation and the accumulation of MDA that elevates collagen synthesis in hepatic fibrosis. Thus, oral administration of 250 or 500 mg/kg of beetroot extract ameliorates liver injury through retardation of apoptosis mechanism or secondary necrosis (Fidelis E. Olumese, H. A. Oboh, 2021).

Betain protects against N-nitrosodimethylamine (NDEA)-induced liver injury and increases the activity of phase II enzymes such as NAD(P)H:quinone oxidoreductase 1 (NQO1) and glutathione S-transferases (GST) by activation of the nuclear factor erythroid-2-related factor 2 (Nrf2)-antioxidant response element (ARE) pathway. N-nitrosodimethylamine (NDEA) are found to have hepatocarcinogenic effect. And beetroot juice, in very small dose proves to provide anticarcinogenic action. The principle mechanism of red beetroot pigment, betacyanin (of which 75-95% is betanin) in the regulation of the cellular defence systems against oxidative and electrophilic stress by activation of enzymes that detoxifies and eliminates reactive oxygen species (ROS), reactive nitrogen species and electrophiles through conjugation and excretion is seem to be performed by the nuclear factor erythroid-2-related

factor 2 (Nrf2) –antioxidant response element (ARE) pathway. It is found that both short interval as well as long term treatment with beetroot extracts helps in delaying N-nitrosodimethylamine (NDEA) induced tumour onset which thus helps in protection of DNA damage by NDEA-derived electrophiles or ROS through the induction of expression of phase II enzymes that are responsible for detoxification and elimination of xenobiotics and reactive metabolites which are involved in cells and tissues damage and injury. And the Nrf2–ARE pathway is mainly involved in the induction of expression of phase II detoxification enzymes and other cytoprotective proteins. And here, Betanin in a dose dependent manner helps to increase the expression of Nrf2 and led to activation of the pathway by increasing the translocation from the cytosol to the nucleus, followed by binding to ARE sequences as found in human liver epithelial THLE-2 cells. Also extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK), c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK) and serine/threonine kinase (AKT) signaling pathways in human liver epithelial cells THLE-2. THLE-2 cells are also responsible for activation of Nrf2 expression. Similar mechanism can also be seen in procyanidin B2 and quercetin. This metabolic activity is also seen in HepG2 cells but very less in comparison to THLE-2 cells. These THLE-2 cells phase II activity is seem to be enhanced by betanin but the phase I activity is reduced.

Paraquat, a toxic herbicide used in modern agriculture for weed control, if accidentally exposed to human by ingestion can lead to poisoning by lungs, liver or kidney damage, if inhaled can lead to lung damage. Since its first introduction into agriculture in 1962, numerous human deaths have been reported by accidental or voluntary ingestion. The toxic effect of paraquat is based on induction of reactive oxygen species (ROS) i.e. increased production of free radicals that causes oxidative stress and an imbalance between ROS production and the anti-oxidative ability of biological systems (Liu et al., 2011) that leads to damage of molecular structures, functioning of cell and so on. Paraquat induced liver toxicity evidences with histological changes, elevated serum aspartate aminotransferase and alanine aminotransferase levels, also elevation of cytochrome P450 3A2 mRNA expression and mitochondrial damage that includes swelling of mitochondrial membrane, reduction of mitochondrial cytochrome C along with reduction in apoptosis-inducing factor protein levels. Betanin can have protective effect against paraquat-induced liver damage by either inhibiting CYP 3A2 expression or providing protection to mitochondria. Paraquat is transported into the lungs by active transportation against a concentration gradient via delicate polyamine uptake system, which is the cause for pneumonitis and lung fibrosis development. Other than lung,

paraquat can also exert toxic effects against other organs such as the liver (Costa et al., 2013; Pourahmad et al., 2011). And since the xenobiotics gets metabolised in the liver, the chances for production of ROS is more and thus the risk for liver damage is also increased due to paraquat poisoning. Betanin, which has a good anti-oxidant property can have antipoisoning effect against paraquat, since the mechanism of paraquat poisoning is oxidative stress (Costa et al., 2013; Suntres, 2002; Sreekanth et al., 2007).

Betanin as protective effect against lung injury

Acute lung injury, which is a frequent complications in critically ill patient populations for significant morbidity and mortality, that is responsible for both vascular endothelium as well as alveolar epithelium injury. Acute lung injury as well as acute respiratory distress syndrome are responsible for acute respiratory failure with prominent morbidity and mortality that causes disruption of both the lung endothelium along with the epithelial barrier (Elizabeth R. Johnson, B.S. and Michael A. Matthay, M.D., 2009). One of the important factor responsible for acute lung injury is oxidative injury to the lung mediated by ROS such as superoxide anion radicals (O_2^-), hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), hydroxyl radicals (OH^-) and hypohalous acids like HOCl along with reactive nitrogen species such as nitric oxide (NO), peroxynitrate ($ONOO^-$) are responsible for oxidation (or nitration) of proteins and lipids. These reactive oxygen or nitrogen species leads to acute lung injury by various mechanism such as direct DNA damage; lipid peroxidation with formation of vasoactive and proinflammatory molecules like thromboxane; oxidation of proteins that leads to altered protein activity, release of protease, inactivation of antioxidant and antiprotease enzymes; and altered transcription factor (NF- κ B) that enhances the expression of proinflammatory genes (Chung Wai Chow, Maria Teresa Herrera Abreu, 2003). Paraquat (1,1-dimethyl-4,4-bipyridinium dichloride) which is a globally used quaternary nitrogen herbicide, known for its high effectiveness and low remnant in crops, through many cases has been found to be highly toxic for humans and animals if absorbed via ingestion, skin contact, or inhalation. The symptoms of paraquat poisoning depends upon the amount consumed of which the most significant poisoning feature is lung damage as it accumulates mostly in this organ in comparison to other that leads to severe anoxia followed by death. After accumulation, paraquat undergoes a NADPH-dependent one-electron reduction to produce free radical form that readily reacts with molecular oxygen to reform the cation and consequently produce superoxide anion(O_2^-) radicals. These oxygen radicals leads to further reduced to generate hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and highly toxic hydroxyl radicals (HO^-) that can directly damage

vital cellular constituents (L L Smith, Hum Toxicol, 1987). Since the pathway which is involved in lung injury by paraquat is oxidative stress, use of antioxidants as a treatment for paraquat poisoning can be focused. The antioxidative functioning of natural pigments such as betalains is being well known of which betanin (betanidin 5-O- β -D-glucoside, red), the most generous betalain component found in red beetroot (*Beta vulgaris* var. *rubra*) and various other species such as amaranthus, rose and cactus pear is found to contain phenolic as well as cyclic amine groups which make them a perfect electron donors that make betanin exceptionally high free-radical scavengers. Since paraquat is an electron acceptor, which after reduction, immediately donates an electron to oxygen and gets converted into superoxide anion and a series of more toxic reactive oxygen species, while betanin is a good electron donors with high free-radical scavenging ability, thus neutralizing the toxic effect of paraquat herbicide. Paraquat primarily targets the alveolar epithelium in the lung for toxicity that serves as a barrier forming tight junctions, which leads to blockage of the paracellular space and regulation of the passage of ions and macromolecules via paracellular pathway. The tight junctions consisting of a series of interactive proteins and receptors such as zonula occludens 1–3, occludin, claudins 1–5 and transmembrane adhesion proteins usually interact in a homophilic manner. Declined expression of these tight junctions such as zonula occludens and claudin-4 by paraquat causes numerous epithelial and endothelial injuries featured by high permeability. Betanin has the ability to inhibit the mechanism of paraquat involved in reduction of the expression of zonula occludens and claudin-4, thus can provide protection to the barrier mechanism of the alveolar epithelium. Paraquat also induces the expression of various inflammation cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-1 β and also activate NF- κ B. Betanin is also seen to have the antagonizing activity for paraquat-induced IL-1 β and TNF- α expression and thus inhibits paraquat-induced NF- κ B activation. In summarising, the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties of betanin are responsible for providing protective activity for the lung from paraquat-induced injury (Junyan Han, Deshun Ma, 2015).

Betanin as cardioprotective

Cardiovascular diseases are the leading cause of death all over the world that comprises a wide class of disorders of which the major clinical manifestations involve peripheral arterial disease, coronary heart disease and cerebrovascular disease. The various pathological conditions that are considered as risk factors for cardiovascular disease involves hyperlipidemia, hypertension, diabetes and obesity as they reduce the detoxification capacity

of antioxidant mechanism against ROS and RNS species. ROS which is generally produced in the process of mitochondrial respiration is important for the mediators involved in signal processing, cell proliferation, gene expression and so on if present in balanced amount but if exceeds due to imbalance between production and its utilization, is responsible for oxidative stress which causes damage to lipids, proteins, cell membranes, DNA molecules along with mitochondrial dysfunction, cell signaling disturbance, DNA oxidation and so on. Thus, oxidative stress triggers the cardiovascular disease progression. As, betanin has already been known to produce antioxidant effect and helps to reduce oxidative stress, its action was experimented on Wistar rats who were given high fat diet for 60 days which lead to altered glucose metabolism, increased glucose resistance, increased cholesterol, damaged liver, increased triglycerides which promoted oxidative stress due to disruption of antioxidant enzymes like GPx, CAT etc. And administration of betanin for 20 consecutive days at 20mg/kg dose was found to regulate the glucose metabolism by controlling insulin level, decrease plasma triglyceride level, restore antioxidant enzyme activities, reverse hepatic damage by reducing AST and ALT levels. Its antioxidant activity is not only based on electron and hydrogen donating ability but also it modulated mRNA expression. So, overall the risk factors involved in CVD progression can be reduced by short term betanin intake (Davi Vieira Teixeira da Silva, Aline D'Avila Pereira, 2019).

Improper lifestyle and eating habits, such as regular intake of saturated and trans fat rich foods, along with habits such as smoking, alcohol, stress as well as aging are the root causes of development of obesity, diabetes mellitus, dyslipidemia and arterial hypertension. These pathological conditions further causes disturbances of the oxidative species–antioxidant balance, thus leads to abnormal ROS and RNS generation as well as impaired antioxidant activity, establishing oxidative stress (Hackam and Anand, 2003; Halliwell and Whiteman, 2004). Furthermore, macromolecules such as DNA, lipids and proteins undergoes oxidative damage due to increased amounts of reactive species, also interrupts redox-dependent signaling pathways in vasculature, that leads to endothelial dysfunction and atherogenesis (Evrard et al. 2016; Forstermann, Xia and Li, 2017). The peroxidation of fatty acids in LDL particles caused by increased reactive species increases negative charge, density, lysolecithin, cholesterol oxide, hydroxide, hydroperoxide content, and cytotoxicity with decreasing polyunsaturated fatty acids, with consequent fragmentation of apolipoprotein B-100 (apo B-100) in them (Kovanen and Pentikainen, 2003). These may further enhance vasoconstrictor substances, like thromboxane and angiotensin II, adhesion molecules and +growth factors,

along with the growth of smooth muscle cells, and disturbs the maintenance of homeostasis and vascular tone (Hulthe and Fagerberg, 2002). Oxidized LDL may also increase arginine methyltransferase I and II in endothelial cells, that causes enhanced formation of asymmetric dimethylarginine (ADMA) and symmetric dimethylarginine (SDMA). ADMA dissociates the enzymes and generates superoxides, while SDMA competes with arginine for the cationic amino acid transporter in the cell membrane and indirectly alters NO production levels (Smith et al., 2018). The positively charged region of betanin having antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities confer affinity towards negatively charged lipid portions ($-\text{CO}_2^-$), interacts with LDL and thus protects it from oxidative damage. Various other protective action includes binding of betanin with the polar head of fatty acids or polar residues of apoB-100, interrupting lipid peroxidation by the ability to donate electrons that first reacts with oxidizing molecules hence protecting LDL as well as interacts with oxidant molecules such as ferric ions (Fe^{3+}) which gets reduced into ferrous form (Fe^{2+}) thus inhibiting OH $^-$ radical formation which is mainly involved in initiating lipid peroxidation, by the removing hydrogen atoms from lipid membranes, due to which the permeability is disturbed, results loss of selectivity for the influx and efflux of nutrients and toxic substances into the cell, that is responsible for damage and death of the cell, hence betanin overall involves in weakening the main mechanism involved in atherogenesis and cardiovascular disease. (Kanner, Harel, and Granit, 2001; Tesoriere et al., 2003; Allegra, Tesoriere, and Livrea, 2007; Kanner, Harel, and Granit, 2001; Halliwell and Whiteman 2004).

Betanin as miscellaneous protective activities

The onset of intestinal ischemia-reperfusion (IR) via oxidative stress can initiate not only local damage, but also acute lung injury (ALI) (Carden and Granger, 2000), that can potentially follow a systemic inflammatory reaction syndrome along with multiple organ dysfunction syndrome (Ceppa et al., 2003). The destructive molecules such as Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) such as hydrogen peroxide, superoxide or inflammatory cytokines produced locally, during the process of IR injury of the jejunum get into the bloodstream and further lead to numerous other tissues and organs damage in the body. The most vulnerable segment organ to IR injury is the small intestine (Chu et al., 2015). Intestinal IR leads to acute blood flow obstruction that can be found in various disease cases such as in case of occlusive disease or in severe hypoperfusion (sepsis, splanchnic vasoconstriction, cardiovascular surgery) that finally contributes to serious intestinal damage (Grootjans et al., 2016). Of the various attempts such as anti-complement, ischemic preconditioning, anti-

inflammatory therapy and lastly antioxidant supplementation that are used to treat the mucosal damage that contributes in a number of pathological and iatrogenic events, antioxidant have proved to provide better protection against IR injury. Generally, the antioxidant activities include a reduction of malondialdehyde levels (MDA) and enhancement of antioxidant ability by glutathione (GSH) (Impellizzeri *et al.*, 2016; Turan *et al.*, 2017; Yucel *et al.*, 2011). Betanin is one of the natural antioxidant that has the ability to alter oxidative stress and lower ROS-mediated damage (Han *et al.*, 2015; Tan *et al.*, 2015; Vulic *et al.*, 2014). Also numerous studies have proved betanin and betalain's antioxidant and anti-inflammatory actions (Livrea and Tesoriere, 2012). Betalain of red beetroot is one of the 10 most potential antioxidant phytomolecules (Azeredo *et al.*, 2007). Betanin also has ability to inhibit lipid peroxidation and heme decomposition *in vitro* even if administered in minute concentrations (Kanner *et al.*, 2001) and has already shown its ability to inhibit carbon tetrachloride-induced liver injury in fish (Han *et al.*, 2014), also found to suppress inflammatory cascade (MPO, MDA, inducible nitric oxide synthetase levels) and enhancement of antioxidant defence (superoxide-dismutase, catalase, glutathione) in myocardial infarction (Yang *et al.*, 2016). Also it shows a strong anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and thus protective effect as it contributes in inhibiting polymorphonuclear leukocytes population activity, a quantitative reduction of MPO, MDA and pro-inflammatory mediators like TNF- α and IL-1 β all of which has involvement in causing oxidative stress (Han *et al.*, 2014) which supports the idea of a protective action of betanin on IR injury. It has been seen that not only local and primary jejunal tissue gets affected by intestinal IR injury but it also has a widespread effect. Local inflammatory response lead by reperfusion affects the gutbarrier integrity which further allows bacterial entry into systemic circulation which further initiates inflammatory mediators. Additionally, distant secondary organ injury develops, that mainly has pulmonary and renal effect, also can affect other organs but to a comparatively low degree (Mura *et al.*, 2007; Zhang *et al.*, 2008). Enhanced vascular permeability of lungs result in pulmonary injury by the influence of inflammatory mediators such as ROS, cytokines and systemic endotoxemia (Kostopanagiotou *et al.*, 2008). Intestinal IR injury damages the pulmonary tissue especially by neutrophil recruitment and activation that causes gut-mediated pulmonary damage (Koike *et al.*, 1993). Betanin can also be beneficial for the protection of distant organs mainly lung in comparison to its local protective effect on intestinal IR injury. Betanin treatment can reverse the gradual increase of both LII and IST during the reperfusion period in pulmonary tissue with 100% improvement in pulmonary histological structure along with a 25% thinner interalveolar septa and 20%

larger AS available for respiration. Moreover, studies have also proved betanin administration has the ability to counteract the expansion of the mast cells population. In conclusion, betanin has a beneficial effect on jejunal as well as pulmonary tissue histological lesions caused due to intestinal IR injury. The mechanism includes protection of intestinal mucosa, that indirectly preserves the lung parenchyma. Also betanin pretreatment has shown ability to reduce inflammation followed by intestinal IR injury (Stefan Totha, Zuzana Joncova, 2019).

4. CONCLUSION

Thus, betanin, which is the glycosidic, indoline extracts, obtained mostly from *Beta vulgaris* L. in a concentration of 300-600 mg/kg from the root part, is one of the blessed phytochemical as it has a numerous vital activities such as chemical synthesis, food colourant, cosmetic and pharmaceutical colourant along with various major therapeutic activities such as anticancer activity by the mechanism of lowering cancer cell proliferation and viability; antidiabetic activity by the mechanism of declined production of glucose in liver and enhanced insulin release; hepatoprotective activity by the mechanism of reduction in oxidative stress); bronchoprotective activity by its high free radical scavenging activity; and so on. However, it is also having some formulation challenges as it is readily degradable in the presence of some of the extrinsic and intrinsic factors such as pH, oxygen, moisture, light, metallic ions, storage conditions etc. The degradation of betanin can lead to aldimine bond breakage along with dehydrogenation, deglycosylation, decarboxylation and isomerization.

However, various researches have been found upon its various therapeutical activities study and mechanisms, its stabilizing methods, its use as food colorant; but still its formulation into novel delivery system for various pharmacological action and disease treatment is yet not considered much.

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